

TEACHING INDIAN LEARNERS: MEMOIRS OF INSTRUCTORS AMIDST CULTURAL ADJUSTMENT

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative study delved into the challenges faced by teachers in effectively instructing Indian students within the classroom setting. Employing a phenomenological approach, the research aimed to uncover the struggles encountered by educators, their collective perspectives on teaching Indian students, and the insights gleaned from their shared experiences. Through purposive sampling, participants consisting of teachers instructing Indian students at Brokenshire College were selected. Thematic analysis of interview transcriptions was conducted to elucidate key findings. Results underscored the complexities inherent in teaching Indian students, particularly in navigating cultural differences, varied learning styles, and instances of academic dishonesty. The study sheds light on the multifaceted nature of this pedagogical challenge, providing valuable insights for educators seeking to enhance their instructional practices in culturally diverse classrooms.

Keywords: *Indian students, culture, adjustments, struggles, teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Indian monastic and philosopher Swami Vivekananda voiced education as the process of bringing out the potential that is latent in every human being enlightening that the very essence of education is the concentration of mind, not the collection of facts. In addition, unless curiosity is recognized and given its due place, creativity will find a back seat in the educational process. Thus the ultimate aim of any teaching method should be

to develop concentration of mind and awaken curiosity for independent and logical thinking which ultimately will reach the higher level of research which is also a part of education (Rytzler, 2017). Education is one of the important instruments for improving the quality of people, society, and nation and it also helps in meeting the challenges of fast developments in the world (Haleem, et. al., 2022)

Mahatma Gandhi opined that illiteracy is a curse in a country and the lack of universal illiteracy is one of the major factors which has thwarted total development in India since independence. Literacy and education have been termed as the best defense of society against the rising population, poor health, social strife and tensions, poor economic conditions, higher child mortality rate, and education (Bango & Ghosh, 2023). In congruence with the idea presented, Bashar (2017) emphasized that education is essential for all and is fundamental to our all-round development whether material or spiritual. Education has an accelerating role and refines sensitivities and perceptions that contribute to national cohesion, a scientific temper, and independence of mind and spirit thus furthering the goals of socialism, secularism, and democracy enshrined in our constitution.

In a nutshell, literacy and education is the nucleus of social and national development (Beecher, 2023). The number of international students attending colleges and universities in the US has increased significantly (Witherell & Clayton, 2014). During the academic year of 2013 – 2014, there were 886,052 international students enrolled in US universities and colleges, which constituted an increase of 8.1%. More specifically, Mesidor and Sly (2016) statistically reviewed the number of international students increased by 72% (514,723 to 886,052 students) from 2000 to 2014.

For decades, the Philippines has been the home of many Indian migrants. Through the years, Indian learners have established communities and business networks and forged ties with Filipinos in various parts of the country. It is commonly believed that only two prominent Indian communities exist in the country: the Sikhs and the Punjabis. However, these two groups belong to a larger population of diaspora Indians which also includes Filipinos of Indian origin and a small number of other Indian ethnic groups. There are also more recent arrivals consisting of transnational Indians, many of whom are information technology (IT) professionals and students (Santarita, 2015).

According to the Indian embassy, more than 8,000 Indians are studying science and medicine in the Philippines. Among them, the maximum, around 4,500, are in Davao Medical School Foundation (DMSF) in Davao City, Southern Philippines. Designated Indian Ambassador Jaideep Mazumdar to the Philippines interacted with Indian students at Davao Medical School Foundation. Currently, these Indian learners are studying medical courses. DMSF is followed by Perpetual Dalta in Las Pinas which has about 1,800 Indian students (Digal, 2017).

Research Questions

This study aims to explore the experiences of the instructors in teaching Indian learners about Indian learning traditions and the role played by teachers in imparting education. Insights that will be gathered play a vital role in enhancing education, spreading literacy, and developing educational interventions. This paper sought to determine the teaching experiences:

1. What are the actual experiences and challenges of the teachers in teaching Indian students?
2. What are the insights and lessons learned in teaching their Indian students?

METHODOLOGY

Philosophical Assumptions of the Study

Narrative analysis differs from other qualitative methodologies by focusing on how an individual retells their lived experiences using their sense of reality and language. Narrative sharing reveals an understanding of self, others, and situations, all critical to action and interactions (Ntinda, 2020). A narrative analysis researcher, or narrative analyst, is interested in how a participant recalls events, links or relates activities, and shares those accounts with someone else (Parish & Candon, 2016). Narrative analysis is thus most concerned with how an individual's story is being told, who is involved in the story, and in which way the story is being revealed.

Narratives and stories matter and contribute to sociological knowledge because of their dynamic qualities, including the sharing of cultural ideologies and hegemonic assumptions. Narratives are cultural productions reflecting specific social times; narratives are performances (Vaara et. al., 2016). Moreover, sharing narratives is especially significant because it reveals influential social relationships, particularly reflecting power and resistance. Narrative analysis is a mutual enterprise; power does not just exist in the hands of the researcher, but is shared. Thus, the narrative relationship between researcher and participant challenges traditional power structures, demonstrating that power enters interactions at various locations with multiple meanings. Power is also visible in the way the body shares information, and interactions; the self is a direct result of power (Dillon, 2014).

Narrative analysis exists on five levels; individual, interpersonal, institutional, cultural, and social (Parish & Candon, 2016). The narrative stretches across these levels. Individuals possess a story, which is shared interpersonally. Institutionally, stories use social institutions to shape our identities, such as education, employment, and the government. Cultural and social constructs produce our identities, and we are the actors in our stories. Moving through these levels, the stories contain past events and actors,

have an order or structure, and endure some kind of struggle. Narrative analysis involves connecting events, and making sense of individual interactions that produce social relations and associations that create themes, patterns, and consequences (Collin & Stockton, 2018).

Research Design

This study made use of a qualitative method with the application of narrative analysis and is descriptive; thus, any facets of information that may be derived are all fluid, subjective, and given from the perspective of the participants and based upon their understanding. This study was conducted to gain an understanding of the teachers' experiences in teaching Indian learners through their day-to-day experiences in the academe.

The qualitative research explored and described how instructors react to their Indian students. The research technique used is a modified Van Kaam method described by Neubauer et. al. (2019) based on recorded and transcribed interviews using in-depth interview questions to capture the day-to-day experiences of Indian students' teachers.

Research Participants and Sampling

The target participants of this study are 10 teachers coming from the tertiary level. Each participant was assigned a pseudonym that in no way reveals the informant's true identity. Samples of potential participants represented the target population of interest, with the sampling frame comprised of the population from which the sample is drawn (Martínez-Mesa et. al., 2016). The participants are purposefully chosen so that the information needed to expedite the study would be the exact data necessary to answer the research questions posed in the earlier part of the paper.

Data Analysis

In the analysis of data, three steps were employed patterned after the study of Miles et. al (2013), namely data reduction, data display, conclusion drawing, and verification which are integrated into the larger essentials of narrative analysis.

During the data reduction, the interview answers of the participants from the audiotape were transcribed and translated. The researchers decided on how to code categories group and organize them. During the data display, the researchers presented them in the form of a figure illustrating the patterns and findings of the data. During the conclusion drawing and verification, initial thoughts about the pattern were developed. The analysis of qualitative data was exploratory and employed a constant comparison procedure (Gale et. al., 2013). All interviews were transcribed and analyzed as they were collected.

Initially, transcripts were read re-read, and notes were taken as board themes or concepts emerged. Subsets of concepts called categories were noted and gradually fell

into the context of the broader themes. Data were analyzed to identify salient elements relating to importance and unobtrusive themes. Data from the transcribed interviews were coded to reduce attributions to the component elements cause, outcome, and links between the two. The intent is to analyze the data and establish common themes, patterns, terms, or ideas that can inform a deeper understanding of the issue surrounding the research problem while articulating a rich description of the phenomenon of teachers.

Data Collection

Many factors were involved in the consideration of appropriate research methods for data collection and instrumentation (Bastos et. al., 2014). The factors included the need for data from subject matter experts based upon the day-to-day experiences and varied perspectives from diverse participants. Creswell and Creswell (2018) identified observations, interviews, documents, and audio-visual materials as forms of data collection. The use of unstructured observational data in different venues as a participant observer or non-participant observer is not available and precludes the opportunity to take field notes or to record data to inform the researchers. The most appropriate and available data collection method to achieve data validity and reliability in the target population frame is the in-depth interview (Sileyew, 2019). The face-to-face interview using semi-structured questions provided the most appropriate instrument to understand the central phenomenon of teachers because most of the emphasis is on the role of the researcher to elicit and represent an interpretive relationship of the world (Rahman, 2017). One-on-one interviews in qualitative research have advantages and disadvantages (Jamshed, 2014). The advantages include reduced time to collect data, greater access to research participants, a commonly accepted protocol for valid qualitative research, and ease of replication of the research. The disadvantages include the lack of direct contact by the researcher with the research participants, the cost associated with data collection involving the recording of interviews and transcription of results, and the generation of a large volume of research data from the transcribed interviews (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Further, the researcher can observe the responses of non-verbal communication exhibited in face-to-face personal interviews.

The research strategy utilized in-depth interviews conducted with a purposive sample from each of the represented occupational domains. All the interviews were conducted personally, recorded, and transcribed to ensure the accuracy of participant responses. Alshenqeeti (2014) defined a qualitative interview as an interview, whose purpose is to gather a description of the life world of the interviewee concerning the interpretation of the meaning of the described phenomena. Phenomenological interviews, according to Bouncken et. al. (2021) can be very lengthy and the use of semi-structured questions can assist in developing a structure for content analysis to promote the generalization of the findings.

Trustworthiness of the Study

Qualitative studies use validity and reliability procedures to test the strength of instruments that measure the phenomena under the study and qualify findings as

accurately representing the data in discernible and meaningful ways. Qualitative research relies on reliability and validity instrument measures. Creswell and Creswell (2018) posited that validity answers the question of whether or not a given instrument consistently yields the same results under similar circumstances.

Qualitative research aspires to achieve trustworthiness during evaluation. Validity and reliability in qualitative research are more a matter of consistency in pattern development than statistical validation of an instrument Creswell and Creswell (2018). Procedures, participants, and readers ultimately decide the degree of validity and reliability of the study. Terms often used to convey a sense of believability in a qualitative research design project are trustworthiness, authenticity, and credibility.

According to Nowell et. al. (2017), the trustworthiness of qualitative research generally was often questioned by positives, perhaps because their concepts of validity and reliability cannot be addressed in the same way in naturalistic work. Nevertheless, several writers on the research method have demonstrated how qualitative researchers can incorporate measures that deal with these issues. The researcher attempted to respond directly to the issues of validity and reliability in their qualitative studies. Many naturalistic investigators had, however, preferred to use different terminology to distance themselves from the positivity paradigm.

Stahl and King (2020) proposed four criteria that are believed should be considered by qualitative researchers in pursuit of trustworthy study. By addressing similar issues, these constructs correspond to the criteria employed by the positivist investigator: credibility (in preference to internal validity); dependability (in preference to reliability); conformability (in preference to objectivity); and transferability) in preference to external validity/ generalization).

Credibility was established through peer debriefing and member checking. Peer debriefing was done through a collaborative discussion among co-researchers where it will discuss matters pertinent to the research and how the research was done. Peer scrutiny of the research paper by persons in authority was done to create feedback for the researcher that was made throughout the study. Member checking, on the other hand, was attained by letting the participants read the transcripts and translations to ascertain that thoughts that had transpired during the interview were still preserved. The researcher made a deliberate member-checking effort to build the trustworthiness of the data, which also demonstrated the researcher's attempt at accountability for his analysis of the realities within the study. This was done through personal discussions with the participants. The use of audit trails also assured credibility. Audit trails consist of raw data and records that are kept regarding what was done during the interview.

Dependability was ascertained by following the correct processes that should be reported in detail, thus, future researchers may repeat the work. It was also achieved through the use of accurate and precise research design and implementation by describing what had been planned and executed. Operational details of data gathering were also accomplished.

Conformability was also addressed by ensuring that the works' findings were the result of the experience and ideas drawn out from the in-depth interview rather than the characteristics and preferences of a teacher. Conformability is also established through data triangulation. It is attained through cross-checking the data with several persons, to search for irregularities in the research data. Moreover, conformability was also ascertained through external audits, who were not involved in the research process. They examined both the process and product of the research study to evaluate the accuracy and evaluate the findings, interpretations, and conclusions supported by the data (Broussard, 2023)

Transferability is applied by the readers of the research. It does not involve broad claims but invites readers of research to make connections between elements of a study and their own experience. To address transferability, the researcher performed some aspects of data management as indicated in the archival log. Included in the archive is the complete set of interview protocols. Transcripts and the translated versions are on the file and available upon request. This access to the inquiry's paper trail gives the readers and other researchers the ability to transfer the conclusion of this inquiry to other cases or to repeat, as closely as possible the procedures of this study. Stahl and King (2020) asserted that generalizability is not the goal of any qualitative research, by ensuring credibility, dependability, and conformability, the study will produce more trustworthy results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The presentation of the results and discussions is organized in three (2) sections. First, presents the experiences and the challenges encountered by instructors in teaching Indian learners, and the second section discusses the adjustments and interventions done by the instructors in coping with the challenges mentioned in the first section.

Actual Experiences and Challenges of the Teachers Teaching Indian Students

The first section tackles the experiences and the challenges encountered in teaching Indian learners. This section consists of the following significant themes: differences in culture, language variations, and witnessing the acts of cheating from learners.

Difference in Culture. The theme emerged as teaching foreign learners is a huge task for instructors as they vary in culture and have different views. Some respondents mentioned:

Sa mga issues regarding sa different ang culture nga akong nakagisnan og ilang dak-an pud so lisod jud siya at first kay kung lahi ko og culture sa ilaha og sa akoo sila pud mismo sa indian naa puy

different culture nga gigalingan oh lisod siya kay somehow lahi lahi sila og attitudes.

(I had difficulties in teaching foreign learners because of our varied cultures, beliefs, and attitudes) – Maricr – Transcript 1

Sa cultural issues, naa lang pud ko sailaha kanang body movement nila na dili ko kasabot and sa pagmove nila sa ulo and then ang isa lang pud kay gina remind sailaha ang cleanliness kay kalat lang na sya mintras di nimo badlungon.

(In terms of cultural issues, I have problems interpreting their body movements like how they move their head. Another thing is their lack of observance towards cleanliness, they won't clean their mess unless told to do so) – Jura – Transcript 5

Language Variations. Moreover, language variation emerged as a significant theme as communication among instructors and learners rises to be difficult for instructors as English is not their first language. Difference in pronunciation is a major problem in understanding one another, as some mentioned:

Number 1 problem is communication so maskin kabalo ko mag English kasabot ko mag English kabalo sila mag English pero ang the way the diction and pronunciation Murag lahi kay sa ilahang culture so most of the time extend jud tanan ears akong self aron magka sinabtanay jud mi.

(Communication is a top problem. Even if I am fluent in English as they are, we still differ in diction and pronunciation, so I have to extend my ears for us to understand each other) – Kora – Transcript 4

Gina encourage nako sila mutingog pag discussion unya kay pag tingog ana kay dili man ko kasabot sa ilang mga gina pang yaw-yaw na diya nako na naschock na murag naa juy language variation so kailangan jud nako muduol sa ilaha para makasabot sila ug makasabot ko.

(Whenever I encourage them to speak in class during discussions, we have difficulties in understanding each other. That's why I need to listen attentively for us to understand each other) – Jura – Transcript 5

Witnessing the Acts of Cheating from Learners. Further, the instructors of Indian learners also encountered problems relating to cheating on tests. The theme emerged as respondents mentioned:

Negative experiences same lang cheating mao man jud na to the point makuan nimu imong self nga naa pabay kulang.

(I have negative experiences especially when they cheat, and I question my capabilities as a teacher) – Kyaa – Transcript 2

Very common kaayo ang cheating so I've been telling my students to not be grade conscious because if you are grade conscious, there will be a tendency that you will cheat; nonstop ang cheating kung grade conscious.

(Cheating is a common problem which is caused by students being grade-conscious. I keep reminding them to stop this bad doing because it is becoming an unstoppable phenomenon among learners) – Miya – Transcript 6

Kuan kanag dati man gud kay effective sila last batch kay more effective kaysa karon na separate ang mga lalaki ug babae. Kay nag tendency man gud sa karon na batch na same gender sa is aka classroom mas saba mas pasikat unya murag mga ana gud. Lisod sya itolerate ug mas. Kung naa may cheating nahitabo last batch mas nilala sya karon its because kay mag igo tanang batasan sa mga lalaki ba unya ang mga girls ug mga questions or mga nigawas sa exam.

(The problem of cheating and noise is more rampant this year since men and women are in separate sections. The unifying of the same sex in a classroom increased the possibility of cheating) – Maricr – Transcript 1

Cheating is like an epidemic among learners, more students are cheating than not. This is a very alarming phenomenon among learners, especially for teachers, as this also reflects their self-assessments as educators. Some also mentioned:

Sa ka grabe sa ilang friendship, maskin absent ilang friendship ibutang sa attendance ana sila. Pag ihap nako, mangutana ko how many are you today, sobra maning duha. Pagtan-aw nako kay tungod kay naa man pud diay na sa ilahang nakagisnan na magtinabangay pero pati ang assignment. Copy paste lang. Unya maulaw sila mag ana ana lang pud sila.

(They would also cheat in writing the attendance. Even when their friends are absent, they would still list them down. Even in their assignments, they are used to helping each other, so they would make assignments for them even if it is just the same as theirs) – Jura – Transcript 5

Actually at first jud dili sila ay wala pajud tuy cheating. Didtu naman tu nigawas sa ting exam. Sa quizzes sa exam siguro desperate sila makapasar. Ang wrong belief nila is dili nila i-change.

(I had my first heartbreak when I experienced their nature of cheating. I discovered it during their exam. I think they did it because they desperately wanted to pass the subject. I just don't understand why their wrongdoing cannot be changed) – Hara – Transcript 3

Cheating and academic dishonesty are an increasing problem in higher education (Church, 2017). Weinberg (2023) pointed out that it can be an intentional, calculated decision to get ahead, and often, it is motivated by the path to success that they see around them—people cheating without incurring any real consequences.

Figure 1. Thematic Map on the Actual Experiences and Challenges by Teachers Teaching Indian Learners

The instructors of Indian learners were observed to be very driven and passionate about sharing knowledge despite the difficulties and challenges they encountered in teaching foreign learners. To be able to impart learning to learners regardless of the difference in culture, language variation, and the rise of more problems, is their main purpose as teachers. This is a positive response from instructors even with all the arising problems they encountered.

Coping Strategies of Teachers Teaching Indian Learners

The second section focuses on the adjustments and interventions done by the instructors in teaching Indian learners to cope with the challenges aforementioned.

Coping with Cultural Differences. The theme emerged as adjusting to cultural differences is part of the challenging task of instructors of foreign learners. It is of utmost importance to understand each other's culture to be able to understand one another. Some of the respondents mentioned:

Naa silay cultural demands. For example sa mga lesson for them to be able to understand so magstudy pud ko sa ilang culture in a way na naga paminaw ko sa ilahang music, naga tan-aw ko sa ilang movie. Para makarelate pud sa ilaha.

(They have cultural demands. You have to be able to understand their culture to relate it with the lesson discussion, like listening to their music and watching the movies they produced) – Kyaa – Transcript 2

Sa ilang culture mismo ilang gestures ana so mao ng everytime sa akong klase kanang mga sayo na indian students, naga pangutana jud ko ana sa ilaha before na unsa inyung ginabuhay ingun ani sa india. Ana ana unsa ni ana kay para atleast para ana ma open ang akong mind sailang culture. Para dali lang ang among discussion kay murag mu alert man gud sila pag naa sila.

(Before classes, I ask the early birds about how and what their culture in India is, which can be connected to our topic so that I can integrate it into the discussion to make the class more lively) – Kora – Transcript 4

Apart from effectively delivering knowledge to students, the challenge of the coping strategies of teachers especially through cultural demands, which the Universitat Valencia (2013) explained as the cultural uses, habits, demands, and values of the students is considered an additional task for teachers teaching Indian students.

Adjusting through Language Variations. Instructors of Indian learners created various adjustments to cope with the language barrier between teachers and students. A significant theme emerged, as some mentioned:

Unya during the discussion since nay mga words or mga situation na dili jud nila masabtan pero pagmaghatag pud kog comparison kay do you have this kind of thing in india, ug muhatag kog example. O explain jud na namo sailaha kay since naa juy uban na dili jud sila

kayo kabisado unsa na na English. Kay pud mi ginatawag na unlock of difficulties for example kini na word wala diay sila kaila.

(During discussions, I give comparisons and examples with what they call it or things seen in India to accurately explain the topic. As a teacher, you must explain it thoroughly since they are not so familiar with its English terms call this unlock of difficulties) – Jura – Transcript 5

Ako particular ko sa ano oral communication so dili lang ko more of written naa pud koy oral kay basin dili kuan nalang sila haha Tapos lahi man silag culture ako silang sabayan ug kuan ba ilahi. O naa man pud na ilang adjustment period diri kay especially three months or six months diri. Kasabot nana sila na naa sila sa adjustment period so kita mu balance ta. Kiita teacher I balance nato na dili kaayo ta kanang strikta kannng flexible pud ta usahay.

(I am particular with oral recitations, not so with written tests. We have differences which is why I take into account that they are still adjusting like how I am adjusting to them) – Miya – Transcript 6)

It is inevitable for teachers teaching foreign students to encounter language variations. SIL International (2018) further explained that this variation is demonstrated by linguistic differences in terms of sound (phonetics) and structure (grammar). Minor pronunciation of words may trigger problems for teachers in understanding their students.

Eliminating the Risk of Cheating. The rampancy of cheating among Indian learners is also a problem for the instructors. This theme emerged as instructors made various interventions to eliminate this problem. Some of these are as mentioned:

Cheating nag apply pud kog mga techniques so katu Set A set B sa exam kay akoa man gud 45 sila kabook goot kayo mi sa room then sa quiz palang na observe na naku nga in ana najud sila so pare pareha maskin essay kay frst nakung quiz kay essay so wala man jud sila kabalo nga mobasa kog essay then I found out na same word for word period comma same kaayo.

(I have strategies in my exam, like giving two sets for the exam (Set A and B). Since we are 45 in the room, we are crowded. And, I have observed that even in asking them to make an essay, they would still cheat-- word by word, even with commas and periods, they would even copy it) – Kora – Transcript 4

Academic dishonesty, or cheating, is the deliberate behavior or action that interferes with or hinders the pursuit of knowledge (Namango, 2016). This phenomenon

and thinking of how to eliminate this problem are growing problems for teachers. Some interventions were stated above for their strategies on how to eliminate this dilemma.

Figure 02. Thematic Map on the Coping Strategies of Teachers Teaching Indian Learners

Conclusions

This study was conducted to voice out different experiences of instructors of Indian learners and the challenges they encountered, with the use of qualitative research design—a phenomenological study. Instructors of Indian learners from Davao City were interviewed as participants in the study. Relevant questions were asked to draw out significant answers from respondents.

Out of the shared answers from the respondents, three (3) themes emerged based on the experiences and challenges encountered by instructors of Indian learners. The significant themes are differences in culture, language variations, and witnessing the acts of cheating from learners. Differences in culture focused mainly on the struggles experienced by instructors in coping with varied cultures. The next theme that materialized from the data is language variation, which discusses the communication barriers that arose upon teaching foreign learners. The last theme that emerged from the

first section is witnessing the acts of cheating from learners, which presents the experiences of instructors towards cheating among students.

For the second section, the interventions done in coping with challenges, three (3) significant themes surfaced upon discussing the different strategies the instructors made toward the different challenges presented in the first section. This includes coping with cultural differences, adjusting to language variations, and eliminating the risk of cheating. Coping with cultural differences discusses the coping interventions of instructors in their struggles with differences in culture. The next emerging theme is adjusting through language variations, which presents the adjustments done by instructors toward Indian learners towards the problems in language variations. The third significant theme is eliminating the risk of cheating, which points to the interventions done by instructors in the hopes of resolving cheating among learners.

This research study further understands the various experiences and challenges encountered by instructors of foreign learners—Indian learners. Hearing out the difficult experiences of instructors of Indian learners, like any other educator, gives a wider view towards and is hoped to give a more favorable treatment among educators of foreign learners.

Recommendations

The research study focused mainly on the experiences and challenges of teachers teaching Indian students in the Psychology Department of Brokenshire College, Davao City. The study presented different actual experiences of teachers, the challenges they encountered, and their coping strategies in going through those challenges.

The same study is recommended to be conducted but would focus phenomenologically on the foreign learners' angle on their experiences, challenges encountered, and their views on the challenges mentioned by instructors. Future studies may utilize a different approach to qualitative research and a larger scale of participants may be interviewed for data gathering to present more significant discussions and themes.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The manner of this study was within the bounds of seven key principles of ethical research, which include the following informed and voluntary consent, respect for rights of privacy and confidentiality, minimization of risk, truthfulness, social and cultural responsibility, research adequacy, and avoidance of conflict of interest in the conduct and practice of this study, the treaty Principle of Participation as cited by Mbaleka (2019), is reflected in the invitation to participate which ensured that any participation is completely voluntary, and based on an understanding of adequate information.

The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the rights of privacy and confidentiality, and the minimization of risk to

participants. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality.

Each of the participants was advised to have the right to withdraw information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and was requested to verify the transcript after the interview was carried out. This provided the participants the opportunity to amend, or remove, any information which they felt might identify them or they may be uncomfortable with. No interview transcripts were seen by the researchers' adviser before being verified and amended, and the researchers reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms and change names and/or non-significant dates in the interest of the protection of the identity of the participants in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Concerning the protection of participants, it was noted that this study did not involve the use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically, in either recruiting the participants or methods of data collection. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical in ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Love et. al. 2020). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the intent of the study, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and identify the anticipated information that participants were expected to provide. Personal assurances of committed participation, prompt scheduling of the interviews, and personal contact diminished attrition, and non-responsiveness, and ensured adequate participation to achieve thematic saturation.

The informed consent letter articulated the procedural steps to maintain privacy, confidentiality, and the non-attribution of individual responses. The informed consent letter declared that the participants' background information would remain confidential and would not be released without prior expressed personal approval. Restricted access based upon a need to know protects and secures from inappropriate disclosure to enhance the reliability and validity of provided data. All participants were required to enhance the reliability and validity of the provided data. All participants were required to sign and return the letter of consent to the researcher before participating in the research. All hippo's responses are secured in a locked repository.

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